

A Study of Alkaline Hydrolysis of Methyl Nicotinate in Aquo-ethane-1,2-diol Solvent System

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Alkaline hydrolysis of methyl nicotinate has been studied in water–ethane-1,2-diol solvent system from compositions 0 to 50% (v/v) of ethane-1,2-diol at temperatures 20, 25, 30 and 35°. The rates decrease with the increasing content of organic co-solvent at all the temperatures. The isocomposition activation energy and the thermodynamic activation parameters have been evaluated which show interesting behaviour with variations in the solvent composition.

This work is in continuation of our previous paper¹ in which the view of Parker² and Roberts³ that the rates of such reactions in which the transition state passes through large polarisation should be faster in aprotic solvents, was found to hold good for the alkaline hydrolysis of methyl nicotinate in water-DMSO. The need was felt to study the hydrolysis of the same ester in varying compositions of water with some protic solvent, and with this in view ethane-1,2-diol was chosen.

Results and Discussion

The specific rate values at various compositions of aquo-organic solvent system at different temperature are given in Table 1. The k values decrease with the increase in the organic co-solvent content in the reaction medium at all temperatures. This is in accordance with the qualitative predictions of Hughes and Ingold⁴ theory. Alkaline hydrolysis of esters being an ion-dipole type of reaction, the transition state is supposed to be highly polar and, therefore, its formation will be disfavoured with the increase of the organic co-solvent content on account of progressive decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium resulting in decrease in the rate constant.

TABLE 1—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANT VALUES (k) FOR ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF METHYL NICOTINATE IN WATER–ETHANE-1,2-DIOL MIXTURES

% Ethane-1,2-diol		k , dm ³ mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹			
v/v	mol%	20°	25°	30°	35°
0	0.0	23.7	30.1	38.2	47.9
10	3.5	13.5	21.9	33.9	37.8
20	7.5	9.3	13.8	20.0	28.2
30	12.2	7.1	9.1	12.0	15.1
40	17.8	4.9	6.5	8.1	10.2
50	24.5	4.1	5.2	6.3	7.8

In order to get a better insight into the effect of organic co-solvent on the rate of the hydrolysis, k values were plotted against the mole percent of the organic co-solvent. It

revealed that the addition of organic co-solvent has a very marked effect in decreasing the rate constant up to about 12 mole percent, i.e. 30% (v/v) of ethane-1,2-diol. Beyond this composition, the effect is almost marginal. This indicates that the addition of ethane-1,2-diol to the medium brings about marked structural changes in the prevailing water-structure and also progressive desolvation of the transition state which in all probability is highly solvated in the water medium. As suggested by Tommila⁵ and Lane⁶, the variation of $\log k$ with $\log [H_2O]$ gives an idea of the number of water molecules associated with the activated complex. Robertson⁷ proposed the equation,

$$\log k = \log k_0 + n \log [H_2O]$$

where n gives the solvation number. In the plots of $\log k$ against $\log [H_2O]$, the average value of slopes up to 30% (v/v) of organic co-solvent was found to be four which reduces to one beyond this composition. This corroborates the contention of progressive desolvation of the activated complex with the increase in the organic co-solvent content.

Values of isocomposition activation energy, E_{expt} and thermodynamic activation parameters ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger are given in Table 2. In contrast to the placid behaviour of ΔG^\ddagger , sharp increase in the values of ΔS^\ddagger and ΔH^\ddagger have been found up to 10% increase in the contents of organic

TABLE 2—VALUES OF E_{expt} AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF METHYL NICOTINATE IN WATER–ETHANE-1,2-DIOL MIXTURES

%Ethane-1,2-diol	E_{expt} kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger , kJ mol ⁻¹			
				20°	25°	30°	35°
0	35.70	32.34	-143.22	74.34	75.18	75.60	76.44
10	72.00	68.65	-23.44	75.35	75.77	75.77	75.77
20	55.67	54.00	-76.89	76.18	76.60	77.02	77.44
30	38.09	37.67	-133.53	76.60	77.44	78.28	78.70
40	37.26	36.83	-140.65	77.86	78.70	79.53	79.95
50	32.23	30.14	-164.09	78.28	79.12	79.95	80.79

cosolvent. Thereafter there is a reversal in their values up to 50% of the organic cosolvent. This is indicative of strong structural and solvation changes resulting in rearrangement and reorientation of solvent particles around reactant molecules sharply affecting the activation process. Complex behaviour in thermodynamic activation parameters towards variations in solvent composition have been reported by many workers⁸. According to Winstein and Fainberg⁹, in binary solvent mixtures both on the part of ground state and transition state possible interactions are involved with the two types of solvent molecules. Solvent-solvent interactions are also very complicated. Alcohol-water mixtures are probably the most complex binary solvent systems. In water a solute molecule builds a structure of a considerable number of water molecules around itself. Such a structure formation around methyl nicotinate is quite likely due to pyridine ring which gets highly solvated in water¹⁰. The structure formation around a solute molecule must compete for water molecules with the existing water-structure. When a small amount of another solvent like alcohol is added, the solute molecule also competes with the structures built around the alcohol molecules. This leads to the decrease in the extent of structure formation resulting in increase in entropy and enthalpy of activation. When the structures built around the solute molecules have essentially disappeared, further addition of alcohol decreases entropy and enthalpy of activation. This is consistent with Frank and Evans¹¹ concept.

Conclusion : This study, in contrast to the earlier one¹, shows that the effect of protic solvent ethane-1,2-diol is quite different from that of the aprotic solvent DMSO on the alkaline hydrolysis of methyl nicotinate both on rate constant as well as on thermodynamic activation parameters. It would be too early to generalise these observations as characteristic behaviour of aprotic and protic solvents unless further work is carried out in different binary solvent systems taking different protic and aprotic solvents as well as different esters.

Experimental

Conductance method was used for determining rate con-

stant using an Elico-CM-82T conductivity bridge. As the reaction follows B_{AC}^2 mechanism, an equation correlating conductance with the conc. of the reactants for a second order reaction having same conc. of both the reactants was found to be

$$\Lambda_t = \Lambda_\infty + \frac{1}{ak} \left(\frac{\Lambda_0 - \Lambda_t}{t} \right)$$

where, Λ_0 , Λ_t and Λ_∞ are respectively the conductivities at the beginning, at time t and at completion of the hydrolysis, k is the specific rate constant and a the initial conc. of either alkali or ester.

Other experimental procedures were the same as given earlier¹. Methyl nicotinate (E. Merck) and sodium hydroxide (Sarabhai M.) were used. Ethane-1,2-diol (Sarabhai M.) was purified¹² before use.

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